

**MILITARY AND PEACE MAINTENANCE IN NIGERIA: A CASE STUDY OF OPERATION
PYTHON DANCE IN THE SOUTHEAST**

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ABSTRACT

Since the return to democratic rule in 1999, the Southeast zone has witnessed different forms of security issues including armed robbery, kidnapping for ransom, wholesale abduction, hostage taking, cultism, communal clashes, herdsman/farmers clashes, violent secessionist agitations among others that poses serious risk and danger to the national security. Consequently, the APC led administration of president Bihari in the spirit of maintaining peace and stability in the region and entire country declared Operation Python Dance in 2016 and 2017 aimed at cushioning the effects of violent crimes and secessionist agitations in the Southeast. The study adopted structural-functional theory thus, the study seeks to investigate the extent to which the Nigerian military have been involved in the nation's internal security, it's legality and impacts. The study predominantly utilized secondary method of data collection and data was analysed by way of content analysis. The study concluded that Operation Python Dance was constitutional and as well significant in the maintenance of peace in the Southeastern part of Nigeria. The study also recommended among other things serious re-orientation of soldiers and civilians, skill acquisition and vocational training of youths in host communities, balanced civil-military collaboration to induce intelligence reports in order to ensure lasting peace and order within the region.

KEYWORDS: Military, Operation Python Dance, Internal Security Operations (ISOPs), Insurrection, Maintenance, Peace, Southeast

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

The Southeastern part of Nigeria is predominantly occupied by the Igbos. The Igbos of Southeast Nigeria, otherwise known as Ndigbo remains one of the Nigeria's major and most enterprising ethnic group accounting for about 18% of the Nigeria's estimated 160 million population. The website nation'sencyclopedia.com gives that breakdown of the make-up of the other ethnic groups as follows: The Hausa, 21%, Yoruba 21%, Fulani 12%, Ijaw 10%, Kanuri 4.1%, Ibibio 3.6%, Tiv 2.5%, and others, 18.7% (Nworah, 2011).

The people of Southeast Nigeria are globally recognized to be enterprising and industrious. Olanrewaju Akinpelu Olutayo captured it in his paper-The Igbo entrepreneur in the political economy of Nigeria (1999) where he posited that the Igbo, when compared to the other major ethnic groups in Nigeria are in the forefront of entrepreneurial activities, especially on the informal sector (Olanrewaju, 1999). However, just as in other states in the region, the Southeast states such as Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo states are not devoid of security challenges including armed robbery, criminality, cultism, car snatching, communal clashes and other violent crimes (Sahara Reporters 2016).

These security challenges escalated hitherto, to pose serious security threat to the region. Hence, the administration of president Muhammadu Buhari with his constitutional powers as commander-in-chief of the armed forces of the federal

republic of Nigeria, deployed troops in the region to restore normalcy.

Aoua and Nwagu (2013) were of the view that armed violence has risen to a crescendo in the region characterized by spikes in communal violence and more persistent low-grade struggle amongst vigilante and criminal networks. Furthermore, they stated these have been partly fuelled by the high levels of drug consumption in the region, the long-term legacies of the civil war and also by inter-religious clashes.

However, empirical observation shows that these security challenges invariably heightened especially between the third and last quarter of the year when most of the population are already calculating their economic gains in preparation of Christmas festivities. Therefore, in compliance with her statutory roles, the military upon the directive of the commander-in-chief (president Buhari) rolled out her arsenal- Operation Python Dance to run from 27 November through 27 December, 2016. Basically, to aid the police and other civil authorities whose competence appears insufficient and incapacitated in the face of crimes and also to ensure a hitch-free yuletide celebration said the COA, Lt. Gen. Turku Buratai, (The Sun, Nov 27, 2016).

Accordingly, the Nigerian Army in particular received so many accolades from various international and local groups including other eminent persons for their doggedness and sagacity in the course of eliminating violent crim and also, for embarking on road rehabilitation and free medical outreach as well as providing learning materials to primary school pupils in some communities within the Southeastern states. However, the economic activities that were peculiar to the region began to return to normal but gradually declining as a result of microcosmic remains of crimes such as pocket picking , car snatching, human trafficking, outright abduction, phone/hand bag snatching, cultism among others propelled the federal government to announce the declaration of Operation Python Dance as an annual event in the Southeast Nigeria.

The exercises Operation Python Dance began on September 15 and ended on October 14, 2017 in the four Southeast states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo triggered off various contending views regarding the nature, character and legal standing of the military exercise in the subregion (Vanguard, October 15, 2017). Meanwhile, it was believed to some groups and sections of the subregion that the Operation Python Dance 2 translated Egwu-Eke 2 in Igbo dialect however, was a ploy to disintegrate and decimate the widespread activities of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) in the Southeast. While others were of the view that the exercise was truly security wise to the subregion.

Ujumadu and Okoli (2017) similarly posited that Operation Python Dance 2 met a stiff opposition from the new proscribed Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), which applied its propaganda machinery to the fullest which more or less thwarted the military exercise.

More so, it was in the spirit of reducing the pressure and critics particularly from MASSOB and IPOB that the COAS through Deputy Director, Public Relations 82 Division, Nigeria Army, Enugu, Col. Sagir Musa made known to the public that Operation Python Dance is a routine military exercise and would stage on the region every year as an annual event (Punch, September 17, 2017). This, the citizens of Southeast are out to welcome the soldiers with open arms come 2018 for Operation Python Dance 3 (Egwu-Eke 3).

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

In recent time, the All Progressive Congress (APC) led government headed by President

Muhammadu Buhari saw the Southeastern part of the country as becoming a breeding ground of all manner of violent crimes resulting to high level of political and economic instability in the region. Hence the President by virtue of his constitutional powers as provided in section 218(1) of the constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria declared Operation Python Dance with the aim of arresting the major security challenges posing great danger to the polity. Meanwhile the legal standing and modus operandi of the military exercise have aroused several contending views from within and outside the region (Sahara Reporters, September 19,2017). It therefore become vital to study the military and peace maintenance in Nigeria with specific focus on Operation Python Dance in the Southeastern part of Nigeria.

Research Questions

In view of the above problems, the questions that can be asked to enable us achieved the purpose of this study are stated as follows;

1. What are the constitutional bases of the Operation Python Dance in the Southeast?
2. What are the roles and character of the military and peace maintenance in the Southeast?
3. What are the impacts of the Operation Python Dance in the Southeast ?

1.3 Objective of the study

Essentially, objective or purpose refers to the major things the researcher intends to do in order to provide answer to the problem(s) noted in the statement of problems (Biereenu-Nnabugwu;2006:430).

The following are the specific goals the research intend to achieve in the study:

1. To ascertain the constitutional basis of the Operation Python Dance in the Southeast.
2. To investigate the role and character of the military and peace maintenance in the Southeast.
3. To explore the impact of Operation Python Dance in the Southeast.

1.4 Scope of the Study

This study concern itself with the military and peace maintenance in Nigeria; a case study of Operation Python Dance in the Southeast states including Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo states.

1.5 Significance of the Study

According to Biereenu-Nnabugwu (2006:430) significance of the study are essentially the list of the benefits of the study...if there is no significance or the significance is too marginal, then there may be no need to embark on the study in first instance.

In the light of the above, the study is important in the following ways:

The study on military and peace maintenance in Nigeria; A case study of Operation Python Dance in the Southeast will ultimately add to the existing literature or body of knowledge concerning the constitutional role of the military and the legal implications of Operation Python Dance in the Southeast.

The study will also be significant for the purpose of literature review of future research.

The study will also serve as a compass to guide the Nigerian military in future exercises such as Operation Python Dance 3, Operation Crocodile Smile etc.

More so, to the entire public, the study will also contribute to the re-orientation of the military as well as the civilians on the need to collaborate so as to combat serious security challenges posing great danger to the society.

Finally, the study will sensitize the mass public against the illegality allegations levied on the Operation Python Dance and the propagandist assumption surrounding the exercise.

1.6 LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Biereenu-Nnabugwu (2006:52) literature review is a fundamental part of any study. It is a systematic examination or analysis of documents containing information about the problem being investigated or studied.

However, the ultimate aim of literature review or critically assessing existing literature is to identify gap-in-knowledge. Identification of gap-in-knowledge necessitated the need for research against dabbling on already established knowledge.

1.6.1 The Involvement of the Military in Internal Security Operations

Simply, the military refers to the tripartite division of the profession of the arms, viz the Army, Navy and Airforce. Together, these institutions constitute the custodian of the national security of a nation. They are expected to work in complementary unison in discharge of their duties towards ensuring the protection of the country's territorial integrity and sovereignty (Onuoha, 2014).

In effect, departmentalization of the military into Army , Navy and Airforce and their functional specialization on land, seas and air respectively becomes inequitable so as to ensure internal territorial integrity devoid of external invasion (Udenta,1994).

In the light of the above, it suffices to state that the military is however, duty bound to protect the boundaries and territorial integrity of a sovereign-state. However, the situation on African experience is a different ball game. It is important to note the military institution is an important institution in the society that could assist in the maintenance of stability through the protection of the territorial integrity of the state. This unusual happens when the institution chooses to abandon its traditional responsibility and then decides to embrace the option of forcefully taking over the responsibility of civil authorities or perhaps, usurping the state power. The issue therefore is how we can keep the military permanently in the barracks in order for them to perform their traditional role as well as disengaged from politics (Babatunde, 2015).

Adesina (1999) in an attempt to object the authoritarian or totalitarian view of Babatunde (2015) on the traditional role of the military, argued that the military is an offshoot of the need to secure the territorial boundaries of the state. Adesina (1999) further argued the military is called forth by the need to enhance the security of a nation's economic, social and political institutions against threat arising from other independent state.

In conformity with Adesina (1999), the primary duty of the military traditionally is to defend a nation's territorial integrity and against external aggression. However, certain exigencies would warrant the deployment of the military to internal security operations (ISOPs), to complement the efforts of the police. Soldiers could also assist civil authorities in efforts to curtail conflicts on humanitarian disaster (The Tides, 2011).

In effect, there is no doubt that the military is an institution of conflict resolution just as it is an instrument of foreign policy. Such influence has its roots in military power

(Thucydides, 1959).

Accordingly, the military involvement in the internal security operation is inevitable as the need for higher level aggression continues to reveal itself. Although, this has been the case since Nigeria was formed and it also continued throughout the colonial period, the violent occurrence of terrorism witnessed in the country has further justified the need for military participation in internal security geared towards peace maintenance and stability (Peterside, 2014).

According to section 217(2)(c) of the 1999 constitution of Nigeria, which forms the basis of the Involvement of the military in Internal security operations in Nigeria provides thus relation to the roles of the military in Nigeria, "suppressing insurrection and acting in civil authorities to restore order when called upon to do so by the President but subject to such conditions as maybe prescribed by an Act of the National Assembly" (1999 CFRN).

Similarly, section 217(2)(c) of the 1999 CFRN was reinforced by section (8)(1) and (3) of the Armed Forces Acts, Law's of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004, it's stressed that this presupposes the troops have to use necessary force to quell crises resulting to deaths, injuries and damages of properties. Other highlights of the Roles of Engagement (ROE) includes:

a. The principle of minimum force and proportionality which must be applied at all times: whenever operational situation permits, every reasonable effort shall be made to control the situation through measures short of using force, including personal contact and negotiations; the use of lethal force shall only be resorted to if all other means to control the situation have failed or in the case of unexpected attack or suspected

Improvised Explosive Device (IED) attack during which could lead to loss of life or serious injury to personnel; and that any force applied must be limited in its intensity and duration; it must also be commensurate with the level of threat posed.

b. Force shall be used only when absolutely necessary to achieve an immediate aim; the decision to open fire shall be made only on orders and under the control of the on scene commander, unless there is insufficient time to obtain such order for which, however, the opening of fire of a soldier, any law-abiding member of the public and/or property of which it is our duty to protect is in grave danger; fire must be aimed and controlled. Indiscriminate firing is not permitted.

c. Fire may be opened to forcefully stop any vehicle that fails to stop at a check point or road block when ordered to stop for search; automatic fire will only be opened as a last resort; avoid collateral damage; after fire has ceased, render medical assistance and record details of incident both in writing and using audio/visual equipment whether or not a casualty has been recorded; and whenever in doubt, seek clarification from higher headquarters (LFN, 2004).

Akpan (2013) critically stated that the use of military in peace maintenance in the country has resulted to a number of lost of lives, properties been destroyed, fear and anxiety have been created and mutual distrust has been institutionalized.

Azinge (2013:2), meanwhile share similar view with Akpan (2013) and Peterside (2014) when he argued that the military however, is not without challenges of its own as they are not particularly trained for internal security operations unlike the civil authorities and as a result, consistently engage in acts which are not civil enough.

By way of recapitulation, we can safely discern that the military institution is very germane in a polity because it provides the needed security networks to safe guard the national boundaries against external attacks and also, in aid with other civil authorities ensure peaceful coexistence and territorial integrity. Therefore, the involvement of the military in the internal security operations (ISOPs) should not be overemphasized.

1.6.2 The Role of Operation Python Dance in Peace Maintenance in the Southeast

Operation Python Dance which the Nigerian Army launched in the Southeast in the twilight of 2016 meant something special in military parlance. However, its translation in Igbo as Egwu-Eke has exposed the ordinariness of the transliteration. In this regard, Python Dance means nothing other than the dance of a python. Even if we associate it with the snake dance, how does that represent what the army did in the Southeast and which it sets to do soon? As a matter of fact, there is a contradiction between what the python represent and the allusion being made to it (Daily post,2017).

Tropical pythons are generally docile and non-venomous one. Therefore, wonders how the attribute fits the military's operation in the Southeast. Even though the expression, as employed by the Army, has no semantic value, the activities of soldiers in carrying out the operation or exercise in the Southeast tells us in clear terms the intent and purposes of the exercise; it is not about oppression and suppression, harassment and intimidation (The Sun News, 2017).

Operation Python Dance is a military doctrine concerned to put in check threat to national security from the Southeastern region of Nigeria and partly to translate into

action through the instrumentality of a preventive show of military power and intimidation. This Operation Python Dance necessarily has a secessionist- prevention as a major objective as well as show of military force and intimidation as a tactics (This Day, 2017).

Vanguard (2017), in a bid to evaluate the exercise, interviewed the army officials who said the exercise (Operation Python Dance I) was successful such that most of the security challenges such as intra and inter communal crisis, farmer-herders clashes, kidnapping, armed robbery and cultism as well as trading in human beings in the region were grossly reduced to the barest minimum. According to Deputy Director, Army Public Relations, Col. Sagir Musa, due to the intensity of patrols, road blocks, raids and other activities in the military line of operation, miscreants and criminals were denied freedom of action.

Similarly, in a statement made available to journalist in Enugu, the Deputy Director, Public Relations 82 Division, Nigerian Army, Enugu, Col. Sagir Musa also stated that the Nigerian Army is currently on a field training exercise code-named exercise EGWU-EKEI (Python Dance II). " The exercise is meant to sharpen the skills of the 82 Division troops in the conduct of Internal security operations...the exercise is also aimed at combating the security challenges in the Southeast and as well equipped to deal with the rising cases of insecurity such as kidnapping, farmer-herdsmen clashes, cultism, violent secessionist agitations, insurgency among others (Punch, 2017).

According to Abia state deputy governor, Ude Okechukwu, " citizens of the state are now comfortable with Operation Python Dance II", which he described as a "wonderful exercise". Further still, he stated " I would like to tell Avians and Nigerians that this exercise (Python Dance) is not targeted at civilians like the propaganda going on portrays. No, it is an annual routine exercise that soldiers conduct" (The Cable, 2017).

In contrast, Evangelist Elliot Ugochukwu Uko, the founder of the Igbo Youth Movement (IYM) and secretary, Eastern Consultative Assembly, in a press release posited that "what is going on has everything to do with the decision of the federal government to stop the agitations for Biafra, to crush the agitators, and also scuttle the peace meeting Professor Ben Nwabueze initiated with the governors. What is going on is a calculated attempt by the military to scuttle peace process that was largely successful (The Sun News, 2017).

However, the Nigerian Army reported that its troops arrested 106 suspected armed robbers, kidnappers and cult members during the first phase of the exercise in the five Southeast states. "At the end of the Army exercise, available records from the Division Medical Hospital and Service indicated that 10,446 persons, excluding school pupils benefitted from the medical out reach conducted by the division" (Punch, 2017). Meanwhile, one of the upside of the operation a resident said, "the disappearance of hoodlums, who once made life unbearable in the area, resulting in a drop in crime rates as complemented by the Police Public Relations Officer, DSP Ogbonna, confirmed (Sahara Reporters, 2017).

By way of synthesis, we could deduce the fact that the Nigerian military is a critical institution especially, in the area of ensuring order, peace and stability in the polity. Meanwhile, the military institution just like any other institution is faced with so many challenges as identified by Peterside (2014). Similarly, Omede (2012) on his part to addressing the numerous challenges confronting the Nigerian military in Internal peace maintenance mission, asserted that more are expected from the federal government in collaborate with the national assembly to put appropriate measures in place to check the excesses of the military vis-a-vis the civilians in internal security and peace operations.

1.7 Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the structural functional theory to advance its argument. The structural functional theory was propounded by Talcot Pearson, Gabriel Almond and Sydney Powell in the year 1984. The structural functional theory refers to the structures that are found in any system and the functions performed by them. The political system is defined as the various structures and institutions in the society that perform political functions or bear a political decision-making. Political system is just like all other systems including economic, legal, social and cultural; it constantly interacts with other systems in all-inclusion manner to produce result. Away (1976) as cited in Chikendu (2002) clearly defined political system as performing political functions. Functions are observable consequence which follows roles. This, if the structures are there, the functions performed by them can be identified.

In the Nigerian society for instance, some political structure are the National assembly, Military (Nigerian Army, Navy and Airforce), Presidency etc. Similarly interpreted, the military is a structure in Nigeria's political system and one of its main function is to maintain peace where there is civil unrest in high tension which the police may not be able to control. Hence, the government of President Buhari used the military power to maintain peace in the Southeast as well as silencing the activities of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) which has risen to a crescendo. Nevertheless, the way and manner of which the Operation Python Dance was declared in the Southeast zone single handedly by the President without considering the position of the National Assembly and the cases of violation of human rights have put so many questions to the military exercise within the zone. The military as a critical structure in a political system must act in conformity with the law establishing it. Therefore, when this structure act or perform outside its jurisdiction or powers assigned to it by law (constitution in a federal

system), such an action is said to be ultra-vires, unconstitutional or illegal. For instance, section 217(2)(c) made provision for the establishment and purpose of the Armed Forces. In other words, where and how their operation would be limited or structured.

"Suppressing insurrection and acting in aid of civil authorities to restore order when called upon to do so by the president, but subject to such conditions as may be prescribed by an Act of the National Assembly".

In the light of the above, it is crystal clear that the security challenges associated with the Southeast as earlier indicated defines insurrection thus, the deployment of the military in the region becomes inevitable.

1.8 Hypotheses

According to Lundberg (1951), a hypothesis is an unsubstantiated generalization whose validity is yet to be tested or confirmed.

Similarly, hypothesis is seen as a tentative statement, which is subject to confirmation or rejection when exposed or subjected to empirical verification (Obasi, quoted in Biereenu-Nnabugwu, 2006).

In the light of the foregoing, the following hypotheses guided the study:

1. Operation Python Dance in the Southeast is legal and constitutional following the

provisions of section 217(2)(c) of 1999 CFRN reinforced by section 8(1) and (3) of the Armed Forces Acts, Law's of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004.

2. The role and character of the military and peace maintenance in the Southeast includes; Militarization of the polity; Excessive show of force; Wanton destruction of public properties; Dearth of military professionalism; Disrespect for constituted authority.

3. The Operation Python Dance has economic, social and political impacts in the Southeast.

1.9 Methodology

It is obvious that no research can proceed without methodology. This is because there are critical roles methodology plays in scientific studies (Biereenu-Nnabugwu, 2010). Nonetheless, the secondary method of data collection shall be utilized in this study including the use of textbooks, journals, newspapers, Internet services, abstracts or synopsis etc. Data collected will be analyzed by way of content analysis.

1.10 Limitations of the Study

In carrying out this research work, some problems were encountered. They includes the problem of funds, time constraint, inadequate literatures and unwillingness of members of the security agencies to cooperate with the researcher due to corruption in term of bribery limited the research.

One thing that makes Nigeria researchers dormant and docile in carrying out research is lack of funds. Lack of finance seriously hindered the study.

Secondly, the time frame including the time to interview the major security agencies in all the five states of the Southeast, the various groups such as leadership of IPOB, Ohanaeze-Ndi-Igbo and other stakeholders was limited.

Thirdly, inadequate literature review hindered the study. This is because it is a current issue. Hence, only few studies have been carried out on the research topic.

Finally, the attitude of the members of the National security agencies was unfriendly. Simply because the researcher was unable to provide prominent personalities in the society and also top ranking officers in the military that could fast track the possibilities of obtaining relevant information and details.

1.11 Operationalization of Key Terms

Operationalization of concept, also known as operational definitions or definition of terms gives a concept or term specific meaning basically if the meaning is critical for consistent investigation, proper assessment, thorough explanation and correct understanding of the entire study (Biereenu-Nnabugwu, 2006:97). Meanwhile, the definitions given below are the operational definitions of the terms used in this research work.

Constitution: A legal blueprint or framework containing the legal basis of the role of the military during internal peace operation.

Insurrection: A violent activity or action by some person(s) against an existing order.

Internal Security Operations (ISOPs): A peace maintenance operation involving the military in collaboration with civil-authorities in civil related issues.

Military: A force authorized by the federal government of Nigeria to use lethal force and weapons to support the interest of the state and some or all of it's citizens in the Southeast geopolitical zone.

Maintenance: The act or process of establishing orderliness with the use of military force in the Southeast.

Operation Python Dance: A military exercise declared in the Southeastern states of Nigeria to cushion the effects of violent crimes and agitations which poses serious security risk and danger to the nation.

Southeast: This is one of the geo-political zones in Nigeria consisting of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo states.

CHAPTER TWO

A HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF THE MILITARY AND OPERATION PYTHON DANCE IN THE SOUTHEAST GEO-POLITICAL ZONE

2.1 Brief Historical Background of the Nigerian Military

According to Adekanye (1985), in 1886, the Royal Niger Company constabulary was formed with a view to protect the British trading interest. It formed the 1 and 2 battalions of the Northern Nigeria Regiment when the latter was cleared in 1900. The nucleolus of the 3 Battalion of the Southern Nigeria Regiment was constituted by the force raised by Sir. Ralph Moor between 1891 and 1892 called the "Oil Rivers Irregular" later renamed the "Nigeria coast constabulary" with headquarters in Calabar. In 1897, Fredrick Lugard created the West African Frontier Force (WAFF) and the three Battalions mentioned above constituted some of its regiments, when Nigeria was amalgamated in 1914. On June 7, 1956, the Nigerian Regiments of WAFF was renamed Nigeria Military Force. Prior to Independence, within the Nigerian military force, there was only 15 officers who were Nigerians and the rest were Britons.

The Nigerian military like that of the rest of British West Africa originated from the Royal West African Frontier Force (RWAFF). This RWAFF was formed around 1879 and they were used for the conquest and control of the nations and for the consolidation of British colonial order. During the pre- Independence period, the military were employed against the nationalist leaders and were use to harass, intimidate and control rival groups. Therefore, the military, were the coercive instrument of the colonial state and were identified with colonial state and the British empire rather than Nationals of their country. The colonial army was indoctrinated with the law of order and disaster for change, politics and especially, politicians who they inclined to regard as disturbance of peace (Udenta, 1994:222).

The Nigerian military arose as part of the colonial machinery for quashing anti-colonial resistance by the people. It was therefore created to facilitate and sustain colonial rule and exploitation. The first military unit formed by the British was in 1862 called "Clovers Hausa" or "Hausa Militia". Initially it numbered 40 men and rapidly rose to 100 men. This force was essentially made up of Hausa slaves who ran away from their masters to seek refuge with lieutenant-clover (Claudi Welche, 1992:5).

First (1970:362) pointed out that during Independence, the Nigerian military was a dubious inheritance. The Army, in view of shortage importance and awesome potentials in a political system was supposed to be a corporate body with a corporate sense, able thorough discipline, to avoid ethnic or other group antagonism that divided other elite groups. But Nigeria's Army was no better able to escape these divisions and antagonisms. Officers and other ranks alike broke discipline indiscriminately to identify with communal interests.

The Nigerian Army reflected itself with all the divisions, tensions, contradictions and crises of Nigeria society (cited in Udentia, 1994).

Early Recruitment in the Nigerian Military

According to Gutteredge and Adekanye (1985), they averred that the earliest of those recruited into the army were illiterates, run away slaves, non-urbanites, vagabonds and such members of the Lupen class "whose duties were to kill and be generally brutal". The military was therefore traced with disdain and contempt. It was seen as an occupation with low prestige, requiring little or no educational qualifications, worse still their income, as compared with university and other professional work was poor. The net effort was social differentiation to the disadvantage of the military. This is sum pre-

configured, it's consternation, disposition and attitude to other professional, the state and to civil society,(cited in Adekanye, 1985).

In addition, the result of this was that few people had offered themselves for military employment compared to the other occupations. Most Nigerians had preferred; rather to go first, and (struggle to) obtain some educational qualifications which then permit them to get better paid jobs, (Agbese, 1990). However, it is imperative to note that prior to Independence, the educational qualification for entering into the officers corps of the army was similar to those aspirants in other professional careers such as medicine and law. But by May, 1961, when the 'quota system's was introduced into the army for the officers corps (combatants), the basic entry qualification was reduced from credit passes in four subject of secondary school certificate or GCE ordinary level, and the alternation of qualification of Teachers Grade 2 Certificate of the Royal Society of Arts (RSA) Stage 2 certificate became the minimum for other ranks, quota had been reintroduced in 1958.

Adekanye (1985) further stated that this was;... obviously, to accommodate some of the lesser-qualified candidates from the northern region. This involved considerable lowering of the standard. About the same time, the Balewa government put a stop to the existing practice of giving combatant commissioners to university graduates. The later were seen by the Hausa-Fulani ruling group as "intellectuals-in-uniform" who speak "Dogo Tunanci" (book learned). Hence, those who were well educated in the military were such as too Bukuru (too British) and treated with contempt as un-military.

As Jinadu, while paraphrasing M.J. Dark, succinctly pointed; the Nigerian Army was like a "far layer sandwich with different group predominant in each layer". Corresponding to the level of education required for recruitment in each layer. Thus, the bottom layer was predominantly made up of northerners from the middle belt and Borno; the General Duty Layer, consisting of NCOs was also predominantly made up of northerners. But Southners occupied a much higher proportion "among trades men, signalers, clerks and other ancillary soldiers, (Adekon, 1984).

Furthermore, the nature of recruitment in the military from 1961 showed closer links between the interest of the feudal and political classes especially, in the north. Indeed, many of those who get recruited then were secondary school dropouts, school certificate failures or people connected by consanguinity to the feudal class or in whom the political class had interest. Several military Generals who rendered accounts of how they joined the army especially, those who fall within the 1960s recruitment bracket cannot escape this description and qualification.

In this regard, Ahmadu Bello and Mohammed Ribadu were very crucial and played an influential role. The feeling of inferiority as compared with other professions, along with their close alliance with political and feudal classes, does the basis of conscience and congruity of interest between the officers corps of the army and those civilian actions of the ruling class in Nigeria. The further training of that military class in Sandhurst and Aldershot, caused them to be socialized into British traditions and hence, also support and protect British metropolitan interests, a similar faction also exist within the pedigree and legacy which the WAFF bequeathed to them in a way both the dominant faction of the military and the dominant faction of the political class share a common political party which was rooted in class interest and reproduction of a neo-colonial ideology.

Gradually and systematically, the military became less of a professional group and became a political group meant to fill a certain quota of political space defined in geo-ethnic terms and meant to defend a particular ideology defined in a particular context. But the military's claim to professionalism, patriotism and so, gave it a good and credible platform on facade behind which to shield in social and political values without revealing its true partisan character, (Civil Liberties Organization, 1999).

Branches of the Military

Different states established different types of military branches. For instance, the United States of America (USA) has Marine corps different from what we have here in Nigeria as Navy.

However, the regular branches of the military are the Army, Navy and Airforce and to some states , the Police.

a. The Army: The army is the oldest of the military services established by states. In Nigeria for instance, the army came into being before the Nigeria state. The primary function of the army is to protect and defend not only the territorial integrity of the States but also defend the interest of states around the world through the use of ground troops, artillery and tactical weapons. It should be noted the bulk of war in history was on the ground. A ground troops, that is the army, take the greatest Ruskin wars especially, in close combat. The casualty rate of the army is the highest. The army of course see itself as the foremost and the most important branch of the military. Even in power sharing the army gets the highest whether in a democratic system or in a military regime. In most countries, the chief of defense staff is often from the at and most often in military regime; most of the heads of states are from the army.

b. Navy: We must say from the outset that states which do not have access to any of the high seas or any ocean generally do not have a national navy. The navy is the branch of a state's armed forces or military principally designated for naval and amphibian warfare. This includes anything conducted by surface ships, amphibious, submarines and sea borne aviations as well as ancillary supports, communications, training and other fields; recent developments have included space related operations. The strategic role of the navy also include nuclear deterrence by use of nuclear missiles. Naval operations can be broadly divided between riverine and littoral applications, although the distinction is more about strategic scope than tactical or operational division (Wikipedia, 2013).

The Nigerian navy was established in 1914 as the Nigerian marine and was a quasi-military organization of the colonial government. It started by providing the necessary military defence of the British Empire. But contemporarily, the duties of the Nigerian navy are akin to that of the United States and other states. The main function of the navy is the naval defense of the country. It performs it's function through littoral and

riverine operations which include reconnaissance in advance of an amphibious assault; recovery or protection of ships and oil installations subject to hostile state and non-state action; maritime counter terrorism, and offensive action (Wikipedia, 2013).

c. Airforce: The Airforce is the last of the military branches to evolve. This is literally the baby of the armed forces as it developed only in the 20th century long after the other branches had developed. The reason behind its late development is the states could not have evolved this branch of the military until men conquered the power of flight. This was in 1903 when two brothers, Orville and Wilbur Smith invented the aeroplane. More development of the machine modified the operation of the Airforce especially, in surveillance and warfare.

Characteristics of the Military

The military professionalism is a romance with death. Everything is done to minimize casualty in the profession. To accomplish this, things are run in their proper sequence and these are seen in the characteristics of the military.

a. Hierarchy of Command: The military is a hierarchical organization of men and women brought together to defend the state against external aggression and internal disorder. The military is but or a hierarchy of command. There is a chain of command and authority flow from top to bottom. The subordinate obey the superior officers in the stratified system. Opera (2002) notes that the hierarchy of command in the military is clean if we look at different echelon of the military and the ranks of the officers managing them well. Thus, we have the General Headquarters, Division, Brigade, Regiment, Battalion/Squadron, Company, Troop, Platoon and Squad. The Manning of the offices from the top goes like this: Field Marshals, General, Colonel, Lieutenant Colonel, Major, Captain, Lieutenant Colonel and lastly, Second Lieutenant. The hierarchical structure ranks for order and discipline in the military.

b. Unity of Command: For the military to be effective there must be unity of command. The bulk must rest somewhere. This is to say that everyone in the organization should have a superior offices from whom he receives directives and instructions. The importance of this is that a situation where there is discordant voices within the military things will go disorderly and the enemy will triumph. A good example was in 1948 when the state of Israel was declared by the Jews. The cities of Egypt, Syria, Jordan, Iran and Lebanon went to war against Israel but were roundly defeated because their armies were boldly coordinated as the Arab leaders quarrelled about whose officer should be the General Commander of the Assembled Arabian Army (Watson, 1981).

c. Discipline: It is exemplified in the military slogan which says "Obey the last command". This is a measure of discipline in which there is a professional obligation to accept without question and obey without exception all orders emanating from the superior officers. There is rigidity in the military which sometimes do not augur well but then there is always a severe punishment for disloyalty, (Nkwocha, 2010).

d. Division of Labour: This is more or less the functional specialization of the sub-units in which work is differentiated for professional soldiers and non-professionals such as medical doctors, nurses, engineers who are but auxiliary service providers. Division of labour therefore entails dividing the work of an organization into different parts to be handled by units for the realisation of the military overall goal which is the security of the state.

e. Communication Network: The military has a high aptitude for the development of science. For a profession that thrives on surveillance and vigilance, the important of communication cannot be overemphasized. It is a well known fact that it was the military that developed computer interconnectivity that led to the birth of the Internet. Good communication network is used by the military hierarchy to supervise the field commanders and it help to strengthen the military in quick response and feed-back. It also help the military to know when to advance, retreat and check insubordination of the officers.

f. Concentration of Authority: Opara (2002) states that in military there is a concentration of authority with order and direction flowing from top to bottom. This working procedure is known and accepted by the members of the military. Every military personnel has the obligation to go along with others and of course accept the proposals of his hierarchical superior. The consequences of non-compliance could really be heavy.

d. Esprit de Corps: This is the French expression for sense of unity and common purpose, spirit of loyalty and devotion which unites the members of a group, society or profession. It is a source of great strength in any organizations especially the military, which needs to be closely knit together because of the danger they face.

2.2 Historical Background of the Southeast Zone

Southeast of Nigeria is one of the six (6) geo-political zones in the country. The region consists of the following states; Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo states, (Wikipedia, 2018).

Southeast Nigeria is a region of Nigeria that borders Cameroon to the East and the Atlantic ocean to the South. It is the home land of Kwa speaking people and dominant language of the region is Igbo. Southeastern Nigeria as sometimes been called, is also where the oil wealth of Nigeria originated from which has led to environment degradation of it's extreme South in the mangroves, rivers and swamps facing the Atlantic. Although Southeastern Nigeria is often referred to as a region by Nigerians. It stopped being an official region in 1967 after the Nigerian government switched to the state system, (Wikitravel, 2014).

Uchendu (1965) was of the view that Southeast came about with Alex Ekwueme's recommendations. Although it is formerly known as Eastern Nigeria or simply East, following the division of the country into three regions under the Gowon regime (1967-1978). It was in 1967 that more states including Imo and Anambra began to emerge.

In addition, Sylvester Asenguah (2017) pointed that the Southeastern Nigeria was one of the initial twelve (12) states created during the Nigeria civil war. Which later broke into the present Akwa Ibom and Cross River State. Southeast became the name of one of the six geo-political zones in Nigeria in the 1990s including Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo states. He also acknowledged the fact that before the British colonial government, Southeastern Nigeria was home to many ethnic groups such as the Igbos, Ibibio, Ijaw and Efik. These groups mostly had democratic systems of government and several kingdoms such as Nri, Akwa, Akpo (Calabar), Ano Confederacy and Opobo which were huge influences in the region, (My Guide Nigeria, 2017).

Brief Background of the five States in the Southeast Zone

a. Abia State-God's Own State

Abia was created out of the old Imo state in August 27, 1991 with its capital as Umuahia. The state has seventeen (17) local government areas which includes Aba North, Aba South, Arochuku, Obi-Ngwa, Bende, Ikwuano, Isala-Ngwa North, Isala-Ngwa South, Isikwato, Umu-Nniochi, Ohafia, Osisioma Ngwa, Ukwa-West, Umuahia-North, Umuahia-South.

The name 'Abia' is an acronym of the first letters of four groups of people- Aba, Bende, Isiukwato and Afiko (now part of Ebonyi state). Abia state is bordered to the North and North-East by Anambra, Enugu and Ebonyi, to the East and South-East by Cross River and Akwa Ibom, to the South by Rivers and to the West by Imo. It has heavy rainfall of

about 2,400mm per year between April and October, and the most important rivers in the state are the Imo and Aba rivers which flows into the Atlantic Ocean. Abia is one of the nine (9) states of Niger-Delta region area well known to cover the oil producing states of the country. Abia is not just an oil-producing state though; it also add rich agricultural importance to the economy of Nigeria with crops like yam, maize, potatoes, rice, cashew, plantain, cassava etc. The people of Abia are of the Igbo ethnic extraction with their traditional language as Igbo, with English serving as their official language in governance and business. The state has a total of 5,243.7 square kilometer land mass with an estimated population of over 3 million people which are mainly christians and entrepreneurial. They are recognized and reputed to be industrious, highly market oriented and very hospitable.

b. Anambra State-Light of the Nation

Anambra was founded in 1976 from old East Central State with administrative capital at Enugu. A future re-organization of the Nigeria federation in 1991 saw the state divided into state, Anambra and Enugu states with it's capital at Awka.

Anambra state is an inland state; the people of the state are warm, hospitable and extremely enterprising and could be found engaging in trading all over the country. The state is made up of 21 local government areas. The state is largely occupied by the Igbo ethnic group who by nature are farmers, fishermen, artisans, craftsmen and traders. Crops grown by farmers here are yam, palm produce, rice, cassava, vegetable and different varieties of fruit trees among others. They also engage in fishing, principally those living in the riverine areas of the state. While craftsmanship is generally recognized as evident in the iron smiting works of Awka people, the bronze sculptures/arts of Igbo Ukwu etc. The state is also endowed with natural gas, crude oil, bauxite, ceramics and arable soil. Some important cities and towns include Onitsha, Nnewi, Obosi, Ogidi, Abagana, Anam, Atani, Nkpor, Nnobi, Adazi Nnukwu, Adzi Enu, Adazi Ani, Oba, Agulu, Ozubulu, Oraifite, Isuofia, Igbo-ukwu and Ichida.

c. Ebonyi State- Salt of the Nation

The capital of Ebonyi state is Abakaliki. The state was among the new additions made by the then Military Head of State Gen. Sani Abacha in 1996. It was carried out of the old Abakaliki division of Enugu state and the old Afikpo division of Abia state and it's nicknamed "the salt of the nation" for it's massive salt deposit at the Okposi and Uburu salt lakes. The state is divided into 13 local government areas and has an approximate population of 5 million people spread across 5,935 square kilometers. The state is dominated by the Igbos with other minority ethnic groups from bordering states.

Ebonyi state is primarily agricultural and stands out as a leading producer of rice, yam, potatoes, maize, beans and cassava. Apart from agricultural, the states also has deposit of crude oil and natural gas. Fishing is also carried out in Afikpo.

d. Enugu State (Coal City State)

Enugu state was founded on August 27, 1991 with the city of Enugu as it's capital in 1967, when the Gowon regime created 12 states in Nigeria. Enugu remained the capital of the East Central State of Nigeria. One of the three states carried out of the old Eastern Region. The state is an inland state with it's capital in Enugu city. It derived it's name from the capital city of Enugu (translated 'top of the hill') which was recognized in 1912 as a small coal mining town, but be found engaged in trading all over the country. Some important cities and towns includes; Nsukka, Oji River, Awugu, Nkanu, Amakwe, Umana, Achi, Opi, Ezeagu, Inyi and Ngwo (9th mile), Nenwe and Oduma, Lejja etc.

e. Imo State- The Eastern Heartland (Land of Hope)

Imo state, which derive it's name from Imo River, was created by Gen. Murtala Mohammed in 1976, and is also known as "Eastern Heartland". Owerri is it's capital and the largest city. The state is divided into 27 local government areas. The area known as Imo state today was originally part of the defunct East Central State. Imo state got it's name from Imo River, which originated from the Okigwe/Akwa upland.

The state has a projection population of about 5 million with the population density

varying from 230-1,400 people per square kilometres. She has a land mass of about 5,100 sq km and occupied by culturally homogeneous people which are primarily Igbo speaking state with subtle nuances in dialects. She has a very rich cultural heritage which is exhibited in dressing, music, dance, festivals arts and crafts, and the immeasurable hospitality of the people. Imo state is bordered by Abia to the East, by Delta to the West, by Anambra to the North and Rivers to the South. The state is rich in natural resources including crude oil, natural gas, lead, zinc, Iroko, obeche, rubber tree and oil palms. The rainy season begins in April and lasts until October with annual rainfall varying from 1,500mm to 2,200mm. The dry season includes two months of hammattan from late December to late February. The hottest months are between January and March. Other important cities and towns includes; Owerri, Mbaise, Orlu, Oguta, Okigwe, Uzoagba, Emekuku, Mgbidi Nkwere, Agu, Ori, Obowu, Ideato etc.

Security Challenges in the South-East

The new state of Nigeria have witnessed so many security challenges following Independence which was vividly captured by Ajani (2010) as murder, rape, ritual killing, robbery, human trafficking, political motivated killings and assassination of prominent men and women in the zone.

According to the Inspector General of Police, Ogbonna Onovo (rtd) speaking on "South East Security Challenges and Solution" the prevalent security threats in the Southeast of Nigeria today include the following:

a. Proliferation of small arms and light weapons: As we speak, the number of illegal arms in the Southeast remains unknown. It contributed significantly to the outburst of violence in the zone. The weapon of popular choice is the AK47, numerous other types of small arms include the Berretta 0.9mm, light machine guns, pump action, short guns etc. Some of these could be purchased for as little as #50,000.00 whole ammunitions go for 500 naira each depending on the make. The federal government established a committee in 2004 to seize and destroy illegal arms. That carried out various destruction of SALW in Plateau, Rivers and Bayelsa States, where insurgency and ethnic

conflagration were prevalent. Some of these arms found their way to the South-East through illegal means. Also, another committee established by Igbo business men headed by former presidential aspirant, Osita Okereke attempted to mop up illegal arms in the South-East but was largely ineffectual. The federal and state government ought to put in more efforts in the venture. Very stiff penal sanctions are required to curb the menace.

b. Kidnapping/Cultism/Assassinations: One many not be able to trace the very day that kidnapping started in Nigeria. But the aim of kidnapping gained prominence in the sociology of crimes in our country when the Niger Delta region 'militants' adopted the criminal strategy of kidnapping expatriate oil workers in furtherance of their campaign for the emancipation of their region. Speedily, the act of kidnapping was embraced by other criminal elements in the South-East, who criminalize and escalated the strategy to the extent that toddlers and even corpses were kidnapped for ransom. Of course, the criminal elements in the South-East who has embraced armed robbery as quickest way of making big money as their nefarious attacks were mostly on banks and bullion vans, keyed into kidnapping as the easiest and surest way of making money with less risk. The act of kidnapping overtime escalated in all the state of South-East, with Anambra and Imo state topping the chart. This is partly because the youths who ever used as political thugs by some inordinate and selfish politicians during electioneering period subsequently as a means of livelihood after the elections, (Nwosu, 2011).

The violent nature of kidnapping and it's socio-economic implication on the economy of the South-East zone of Nigeria are enormous. Thus, this menace was pervasive in some states and towns in the region as evidence from table one below:

Table 1: States and Towns with widely reported cases of Kidnapping in the Southeast geo-political zone of Nigeria

S/N	States	Town Mostly Affected	Other Areas Affected
1.	Abia	Aba, Umuahia	Semi-urban areas and many rural

			areas across the state
2.	Anambra	Onitsha, Nnewi	Rural areas across the state
3.	Ebonyi	Abakaliki	Rural areas across the state
4.	Imo	Owerri, Orlu, Mbaise	Rural areas across the state
5.	Enugu	-	-

Source: Nwagboso's Field Survey, 2015

From table 1 above, kidnapping was a lucrative business among the youths in the Southeast zone. This is because the menace virtually occurred in all major commercial towns and rural areas in the region. It is only in Enugu state that the incidence of kidnapping was not reported during the review period. This could be as a result of the political will and determination of the Enugu state government to deal decisively with any identified criminal group in the state. This according to some public analysts is based on the recognition in an environment characterized by insecurity.

Though kidnapping as at today has been reduced in the zone through the joint and conscious efforts of the state government and security agencies, but till date, there are still pockets of kidnapping being recorded of operation and initiation rites which involves oaths of allegiance, remains secret. Government should revisit the secret cult law and improve on it. A committee should be inaugurated to ensure elimination of Cultism in the South-East. Cultism has led to the emergence of a group of assassins referred to as "unknown gunmen" who routinely assassinate their victims or settle other scorers in the same manner. Recently, beheading of their target has become the norm.

c. Stealing/Armed Robbery/Car Snatching: Armed robbery could be said to have gained prominence in Nigeria after the civil war, where it was discovered that most arms deployed in waging the war were not returned after cessation of hostilities. It was believed that these arms were employed by undesirable elements in the society to commit armed robbery and other violent crimes. Though armed robbery in the 60s and 70s was crude and loosely organized and deadlier, unleashed mostly on banks and cash -in-transit vehicles. There is no doubt that kidnapping is still a menace and a major challenge to security management and economic development in the Southeast. The

same applies to stealing and car snatching cases.

d. Financial Fraud (419): Through the commendable efforts of the EFFC, this menace has declined to appreciable levels, yet it can scarce away foreign investors. The South-East can do well economically without fraudsters on the prowl. This phenomenon has given the South easterners bad image locally and internationally. The police and other security agencies and all patriotic citizens should tackle the menace by identifying such fraudsters, seizing their illicit gains/properties and prosecuting them.

e. Corruption in High and Low Place/Unemployment/Poverty: One would want to exhort our politicians that while seeking political power on office; they should endeavor to play the game of politics by the rules, demonstrate spirit of sportsmanship, elevate politics beyond ethnicity and self-aggrandizement, and ensure fulfillment of promises made during electioneering campaigns. This will reduce acrimonies and violence associated with politics which often times create tensions and insecurity in the society. The non-implementation of the agreed 3Rs (Reconciliation, Reconstruction and Rehabilitation) after the South-East exacerbated the poverty situation, created unemployment and lack of window opportunity and completely dislocated social and political consciousness of the people. The aftermath was the emergence of non-state actors like MASSOB, IPOB, Bakassi and constant cries of marginalization.

f. Lack of Integrity/Ethical Standards/Adulteration of Products: The people of the South-East should build trust between themselves and other Nigerians, including foreign investors, to promote the belief that South-East is a safe place to establish business. Efforts should be made to erase negative image about the region. For example, the adulteration of consumable and non-consumable products remain persistent in the South-East zone. Sub-standard building material products like iron rods, electrical cables and other wares often cause building collapse and fire out break. Fake pharmaceutical products have killed many citizens over the years.

g. Menace of Non-State Actions: Some unscrupulous persons engage in vandalism of

oil pipelines stealing and damaging of government properties viz transformers, electric cables (underground and overload). Some non-state actions in the South-East zone ranges from Bakassi Boys to MASSOB/IPOB who should ensure security of life and property just like the O.P.C in the South-West and A.P.C in the North, have remained ineffectual, rather their activities led to the killing of youths and destruction of property. Any action inimical to the safety and well being of our citizenry should be avoided.

h. Cattle Herders/Farmers Conflict: Herdsmen/Farmers clashes are very recent criminal phenomenon in the South-East. Today, there is growing and sustained animosity between the two groups and seeds of discord and circle of violence have become a defining characterisation of conflict resolution between farmers and herdsmen in the region. The incident of Nimbo community in Enugu state readily comes to mind as an example of how dastardly and gruesome or unresolved conflict between farmers and herdsmen could be. This indeed is an emerging security Challenges in the South-East.

i. Chieftaincy Disputes/Boundary Disputes/ Non-Indigenous Squabbles (Communal Conflicts): The cases of chieftaincy disputes, boundary disputes, communal conflicts and non-indigenes Vs. Indigene squabbles have long been established in the South-East zone. Examples are in Ebonyi state, Ezza versus Ezillo that took so many lives and almost crippled the state and rendered Enugu-Abakiliki High way impassible to commuters. Another example is Aguleri and Umuleri; Awka and Amawbia in Anambra state. The same applies Enugu, Abia and Imo states.

The chieftaincy tussles in most autonomous communities have turned violent leading to loss of live and properties. It is a shame that today in some communities in the South-East, some citizens are regarded as non-indigenes or settlers and the consequences often become security issues.

j. Drug Trafficking/Human Trafficking/ Emergence of Baby Factories: Drug trafficking has given the South-Easterners a terrible image locally and internationally. Most of the

victims of executions in Malaysia and Indonesia are from the South-East of Nigeria. Every time an Ethiopian airline plane lands at Enugu, it conveys at least to corpses of drug couriers. Most South-Eastern cities are drug infested, have high level of crimes which end up in deaths. NDLEA and other regulatory agencies in the zone should increase their efforts. The same applies to human trafficking and emergence of baby-factories in the South-East. If this is not rippled in the bud , the case of Edo state will be a child's play in comparison to what is happening in the South-East, (The Nigerian Voice, 2011).

2.3 Origin of Operation Python Dance in the Southeast

The Nigerian military came to stay in the Southeastern part of the country with the aim of performing their constitutional role of maintaining territorial integrity and aiding civil authorities in the state against risking security challenges including armed robbery, kidnapping, abduction, cultism, violent protest, herdsmen/farmers clash, communal clashes amongst others.

Prior to the Operation Python Dance exercise, there had been serious cases of armed robbery, car snatching, arm banditry, cultism, hostage taking, out-right abduction, arson, criminality, communal clashes which consequently, stymied the little economic progress within the Southeastern states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo states. Meanwhile, the police command in the above mentioned states were quoted to be on the top of the matter to ensure that culprits are arrested, tried and jailed if found guilty by the court of competent jurisdiction.

However, the exercise code names 'Python Dance' launched by the Nigeria Army in the Southeast in the twilight of 2016 meant something special in the military parlance. According to the chief of Army Staff, Lt. Gen. Turkur Buratai posited that it was about raids, condon and search operations, anti-kidnapping drills, road blocks, check points

and ultimately, a show of force to curb the rising threat to national security in the South-Eastern part of the country, (The Sun News, 2017).

Fundamentally, an empirical assessment of Operation Python Dance 1 shows that it was one with laudable achievement. Above all is ensuring a hitch-free yuletide celebration unlike the experiences of past Christmas celebrations which were bedeviled by serious security challenges posing great danger to the peace loving people of the Southeast, (Daily Post, 2017).

However, the New year (2017) celebration was still ongoing when the news came that some miscreants snatched one Mr. Bimbola's car within the Umuahia axis, followed by the growing demand and agitation for self-rule particularly by the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and other unscrupulous activities that have posed great danger to the National security at large. Meanwhile, the Police and other civil authorities were collaboratively ensuring they stick to the protection of lives and properties of the citizens vis-a-vis their traditional role in the state, (Punch, 2017).

Despite all security measures put in place by the civil authorities, the rate of crimes continued to have a spill over effect on the economic, social and political activities in the Southeast region. Hence, the Army was called upon by the President (Mohammed Buhari) to act according to their defined constitutional allowance. It have been crystal clear that the police were incapable of arresting the issues posing security risk in the zone and country at large.

Accordingly, the Operation Python Dance 2 which was translated as Egwu-Eke 2 was declared in the Southeast by the President through the Chief of Army Staff, Lt. Gen. Turkur Buratai to curb the rising threat to national security in the Southeastern part of the country, (The Sun News, 2017).

In the light of the above, the exercise would be multi-agency in nature whereby the Nigeria Army and other security agencies are expected to synergize and collaborate

extensively.

Above all, an elaborate Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC) line of operation has been planned during the exercise. Interestingly, Nigeria Army Corps and Services would conduct activities such as medical outreach, repairs of roads, schools and other infrastructure across the South-East region. The durable mechanisms be imbued in the overall planning as well as execution of the exercise, to achieve a hitch-free yuletide celebration for the region. Be rest assured of the good will and kind of gestures of the COAS, (Daily Post, 2016).

In addition, Col. Sagir Musa also disclosed that the second episode of the military exercise (Operation Python Dance2) is purely command post, field training and real-time exercise. "It is aimed to enhance troops agility and preparedness across the spectrum of contemporary and emerging security threats peculiar to the Southeastern region, (Punch, 2017).

More importantly, against the widespread believe that Operation Python Dance 2 (EGWU -EKE 2) was a masterstroke to put the activities of the IPOB under serious check. Against the backdrop, Ude Chukwu, Deputy Governor of Abia state asserted " I would like to tell Abians and Nigeria to see that this exercise (Operation Python Dance) is not targeted at any civilian like the propaganda going... It is a routine military exercise that soldiers conduct". However, the Deputy Governor went ahead to inform news men that the citizens of the state are comfortable with Operation Python Dance 2, which he described as 'a wonderful exercise', (The Cable, 2017).

CHAPTER THREE

THE MILITARY AND PEACE MAINTENANCE IN THE SOUTHEAST

3.1 The Constitutional Basis of Operation Python Dance in the South-East

Many pro-Biafra agitators are quick to condemn the Operation Python Dance (Egwu-Eke) as provocative and unconstitutional. It is indeed easy to make such sentimental statements, but what does the law posit?

Section 217 (2)(c) of the 1999 constitution provides that "the federation shall, subject to an Act of the National Assembly made in the behalf, equip and maintain the Armed Forces as may be considered adequate and effective for the purpose of...

(C) Suppressing insurrection and acting in-aid of civil authorities to restore order when called upon to do so by the president, but subject to such conditions as may be prescribed by an Act of the National Assembly", (1999, CFRN).

Suffice to say, the Act of the National Assembly referred to here is the Armed Forces Act. What then is the basis of the illegality of Operation Python Dance as alleged by some individuals and groups? It was the submission of the agitators that before the Armed Forces of the Federal Republic of Nigeria can be deployed in accordance with section 217 (2)(c) to maintain public order, the approval of the National Assembly must be sought and obtained. This contention is highly fallacious and illogical.

The role of the National Assembly is limited to make laws for the regulation of the powers exercisable by the president as the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of the Federation. This is virtue of Section 218 (4) CFRN 1999 as amended and they have already achieved it by enacting the Armed Forces Act of Nigeria. As it stated the powers of the Nigeria Army to maintain public order as encapsulated in Section 217 (2)(c) 1999 CFRN, is to be subjected to the approval and confirmation of the National Assembly.

However, it must be conceded that a careful study of Section 7 of the Armed Forces Act which reads: " the Chief of Defense Staff shall, subject to the general direction of the President and the National Assembly, be vested with the day-to-day command and general superintendence of the Armed Forces".

In the light of the above, the National Assembly is to have a hand in directing the operations of the Armed Forces. Nevertheless, record must be put straight that the Armed Forces Act is made in pursuant of the constitution which empowers the National Assembly in other instances to have control in directing the affairs of the Armed Forces. Forget not that Section 305 of the constitution which deals with proclamation of a state of emergency empowers both the President and the National Assembly to have conjunctive powers in declaring a state of emergency. Meanwhile, the provisions of Section 217 of the constitution should not be read and applied together with the provisions of Section 305 of the same constitution. Reason be that both Sections deal with entirely different scenarios. The Executive President (Muhammadu Buhari) never intended to declare a statement of emergency in any part of the country when Operation Python Dance was declared in the South-East. Hence, approval of the National Assembly was nothing but unnecessary surplus age.

3.2 Civil-Military Relations in Peace Maintenance in the South-East

Civil-Military relations (Civ-Mil or CMR) describes the relationship between civil society as a whole and the military institution or organization established to protect it. CMR is an umbrella concept that incorporate a diverse, often normative field, which moves within and across management, social science and policy scales, (Shields and Patricia, 2015).

More narrowly, it describes the relationship between the civil authority of a given society and its military authority. Studies of Civil-Military relations often rest on a normative assumption that civilian control of the state, although some analysis are more descriptive in nature.

Overtime, the socio-political landscape of the South East zone has become a pointer to civil-military relations geared towards maintaining peace and stability within the zone. Meanwhile, it is the functional duty of the civil authorities to treat and settle civil related issues in the state.

However, the Operation Python Dance (Egwu-Eke) in the South-East is on with various contentious views partly due to the nature of civil-military relations during and after the military's exercise in the zone. Many argued that the civil-authorities were not involved while few were of the view that the civil authorities were fully accommodated in the Operation Python Dance (Egwu-Eke) in the South-East.

In the Nigeria parlance, civil authorities are state security agencies established to arrest civil related issues when issues arises. Civil authorities includes, department of state security, the Nigeria police force, Nigeria security and civil defence corps and Federal Road Safety Commission. The Operation Python Dance was aimed at neither any group(s) nor person(s) but to counter armed robbery, banditry, kidnappings, herdsmen/farmers clashes, communal clashes and violent secessionist attacks amongst others which called for a more comprehensive approach (civil-military relations), (Sagir, 2017).

Meanwhile, the above statement replicated in statement signed by the Major-General DD Ahmadu Chief of Training and Operations, Nigeria Army "this Operation will be conducted with the involvement of other security agencies such as the Department of

State Services, the Nigeria Police Force and Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps", (Sahara Reporters, 2017).

Another Justification to the civil-military relations claims are contained in a statement released on September 17, 2017 by the 82 Division of the Nigeria Army, said "one interesting aspect of the exercise is that it's is multi-agency in nature and execution. Relevant para-military organization such as elements of the Nigeria police force, Nigeria security and Federal Road Safety Commission synergy and collaborated to ensure successful execution and attainment of major objectives, (Vanguard, 2017).

Beyond mere political rhetorics were real facts whereby the total of 15 suspects, 11 assorted arms including 15 rounds of 7.62mm special ammunition and 7 cartridges were arrested and handed over to the police in Abia state during the one month exercise, (Daily Post, 2017).

The information above proves any other contrary view on civil-military relations in the just concluded Operation Python Dance exercise baseless. Meanwhile, what ought to be the bone of contention should be whether their partnership was symmetrical equal and balanced against one party hijacking the terms and conditions.

Be that as it may, Operation Python Dance (Egwu-Eke) was another epoch-making exercise that made the nation proud of the Nigeria Military's determination at sustaining it's constitutional role of defending the territorial integrity of the nation as well as it's commitment to aid the civil authorities to bring adequate security and lasting peace in the South-Eastern part of the country.

3.3 The Character of the Military and Peace Maintenance in the South-East

The character of the military presupposes the peculiarities of the military especially, in

their course of internal security operations.

The most evidential character displayed by the military during the exercise of Operation Python Dance 2 (Egwu-Eke 2) are as follows:

- i. Militarization of the polity
- ii. Excessive show of Force
- iii. Wanton destruction of public properties
- iv. Dearth of Military professionalism
- v. Disrespect for constituted authority

i. Militarization of the Polity

Despite the laudable achievements of the military during Operation Python Dance 1 in 2016, there are still doubts amongst the citizens given the level of Militarization of the South-East states with all manner of heavy armoured personnel carriers (APC) just to ensure a hitch-free yuletide celebration. On September 13, 2017 Sahara Reporters released a press statement by a Nigerian pro-masses activist movement known as "Our-Mumu-Don-Do", they were at the top of the issue demanding for withdrawal of the military from the states in the South-East. " We consider this move an aberration that must be strongly condemned in a democratic environment like ours".

The group (Our-Mumu-Don-Do) further stated that the Militarization of the Southeast Nigeria epitomized by the Nigeria Army's recent invasion of the residence of Nnamdi Kanu and the Abia state council of the Nigerian Union of Journalist (NUJ), were all threats to humanity, (Sahara Reporters, 2017).

Reacting to the development through it's National co-ordinator, Mazi Ifeanyi Igwe, the Igbos for Nigeria movement (INM), decried on the adventurous and animalistic tendencies put forward by the military. The INM co-ordinator re-established his delight

on the previous military exercise code names "Operation Python Dance aka Egwu-Eke I" at about the same time, under the supervision of the Chief of Army Staff (COAS) Lt.Gen. Tukur Yusufu Buratai and his subordinates in 2016. As he succinctly put, "we were impressed as it conformed with the highest standards of Military/Civil engagements and due respect for the human rights of the people, as soldiers only hunted and fished out these criminals from their hideouts, who were handed over to prosecuting authorities for appropriate lawful trials. This operation guaranteed a hitch-free, peaceful, severe and secured environment for business and yuletide festivities of last year, but what we perceived during and after the second phase of the military exercise (Operation Python Dance II) was a different ball game...we are losing too many precious lives to these heartless and blood curdling vampires tormenting our peace, commerce and fast forwarding the dislocation of our social and communal existence so dangerously" (Daily Post, 2017).

However, the militarization of the South-East as we publicly made known, lasted from 15th September through 15th October 2017. Nevertheless, the Chief of Army Staff failed to explain why the Nigeria Army was brazenly assuming the constitutional responsibility of the police force.

ii. Excessive show of Force

Sadly, when the ominous operation started five days before its official commencement date, Afara Ukwu in Umuahia North Local Government Area of Abia State, the home town of Nnamdi Kanu (Leader of IPOB), was quarantined and turned into a theatre of violence. Heavy armoured personnel carriers (APC) were displayed in the show of force, which instill fear and panic into the community and its environs. As the operation unfolded, it became "a tale of terror, bloodshed and tears", (Ugorji, 2017).

Hopeless and armless IPOB members who fell into the net of the Nigeria Army in Isiala

Ngwa Local Government Area of Abia State were subjected to unimaginable cruel, inhuman and degrading treatment. The gory video clips that went viral on the Internet (social media) portraying young men compelled to swim in a muddy pond vividly revealed the abysmal contempt of human dignity exhibited by the Nigeria Army.

iii. Wanton Destruction of Public Properties

To ensure that their atrocities were not reported on media channels, the military invaded the Secretariat of the Nigeria Union of Journalist (NUJ), Abia State chapter on September 12, 2017.

However, the operation Rose to it's highest level of terror and brutality with the invasion of the ancestral home of Nnamdi Kanu on September 14, 2017. The continuous shooting of heavy machine guns by the Nigerian Army on that fateful day caused panic among the peace-loving and law-abiding indigenes of Afara Ukwu community and made them flee to neighbouring towns for safety.

Nevertheless, the violent face off between the Nigeria Army and the members of IPOB in Umuahia triggered off the bloody skirmishes recorded at Aba, Abia and Oyigbo, River State.

iv. Dearth of Military Professionalism

Huntington and Janowitz in their individual works; the Soldier and the state and The professional soldier respectively, argued that professionalism is crucial in the complex relationship between the Armed Forces and host communities. In addition, Huntington argued "there is an interplay between the level of military professionalism and the propensity to intervene in the domain of the civil power, (Huntington, 1952).

However, we are deeply saddened to observe that in carrying out the Operation Python Dance 2, the Nigeria Army displayed an abysmal lack of professionalism that has brought embarrassment and shame to ur nation. The engagement of the military must abide by the ethical standards and rules that safeguard the sanctity of human life and the dignity of human person. Given the sanctity of human life, soldiers in self-defense or the defense of the nation may only kill an unjust aggressor during an armed conflict, if and only if that is the only way to ward off his unjust aggression.

No matter how one may look at it, nothing can justify the killing of armless and defenceless members of IPOB or the inhuman treatment meted out to some other civilians. Even war prisoners are entitled to a decent and human treatment. However, we also need to stress that the molestation and intimidation of law-abiding media practitioners by the Nigeria Army is highly condemnable. The Nigeria Army must not Superimpose themself on the civilian during internal security operations (ISOPs). They should always adhere strictly to section 8 of the Armed Forces Act, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004, reinforced by section 217 (2)(c) of the 1999 CFRN.

v. Disrespect for Constituted Authority

The men of the Nigeria Army while conducting Operation Python Dance 2 (Egwu-Eke2), made their presence known in what the Army said was a 'show of Force'. This show which began at the city centre soon spread to the axis where the IPOB leader resides. The military toured to the palace of the Afara-Ukwu traditional ruler who happens to be father to the IPOB leader- Nnamdi Kanu, fired aimlessly at the palace building.

According to newsmen, the palace building of the King of Afara-Ukwu was re-designed with holes as a result of repeated gun shooting on the walls. The people of Afara-Ukwu also alleged that their traditional stool was desecrated by the troops. All these proves

the character and actions of the Nigeria Army as unbecoming, uncalled-for hence, reparatory justice should be paid back to the people of Afara-Ukwu community in Umuahia.

CHAPTER FOUR

THE ECONOMIC, SOCIAL AND POLITICAL IMPACTS OF OPERATION PYTHON DANCE IN THE SOUTHEAST

4.1 Economic Impact of Operation Python Dance in the South-East

The study specifically focus on the major economic fall outs during and after the Operation Python Dance in the South-East. The following are the key economic impact of the military exercise:

i. Huge Financial Loss: The citizens of South-Eastern part of the country describe the Operation Python Dance (Egwu-Eke) undermined economic activities within the region to a large extent. For instance, Me Ken Anyanwu, Secretary General, Association of Leather and Allied Industrialists of Nigeria (ALAIN), said Aba lost not less than #10 billion within that period because the entire city was on lock down. " A lot was lost because Aba supplies the entire nation and once there is problem in the city, it affects the entire customer base. Patrons from the North and Southwest regions of the country and even those from the West African Sub-region stayed away from Aba within that period said Mr Anyanwu, (Business Day, 2017).

Tony Akudinaobi, a utilitarian artist based in Aba was one of the view that so much money was lost. He said " definitely time is money , so in that context, they lost time they also lost money...(Business Day, 2017).

ii. Decline in Market Stock and Equities: The market closed with 14 advancing Stocks and 18 depreciating Equities, saw Seflat emerging the heavies decline, crashing by ₦24.3k to finish at ₦456.76k per share. It was followed by Nigerian Breweries, which fell by ₦5 to close at ₦170 per share and Presco, which slumped by ₦2.49k to end at ₦58 per share, Lafarge decline by 97k to settle at ₦49 per share, while Oando lost ₦5.75k per share. On the flip side, GTBank topped the gaining chart with ₦1 growth to close at ₦38 per share, while Cadbury moved up ₦49k to finish at ₦11 per share. Furthermore, Stanbic IBTC advance by 30k to finish at ₦39.50k share, and ECO bank increased by 20k to close at ₦18 per share (Business Post, 2018).

iii. Traffic Congestion: Motorist plying the Enugu-Portharcourt express way lamented the heavy grid lock caused by the ongoing Operation Python Dance exercise. Due to the effects of road blocks, heavy duty trucks, buses and cars most times stretch up to 2 kilometers waiting to be screened and allowed to pass the military road blocks. Apart from the Enugu-Portharcourt road blocks, others including, Arungwa junction (144 Battalion), Asa, Isiala Ngwa, Umuikea, Amaobia, 9th mile, Amensea, etc.

iv. Increased in Foreign and Local Investors: This was a result of the high level of security put in place during Operation Python Dance to check mate security issues such as armed robbery, kidnapping, hostage taking, communal clashes, cultism, herdsman-farmers clashes, military-secessionist group clashes etc, that were posing great danger to economic activities in the zone.

4.2 Social Impact of Operation Python Dance in the Southeast

It anchors specifically on the social implications of Operation Python Dance (Egwu-Eke) in the Southeast which are as follows:

i. Free Movement of Persons and Vehicles: The Operation Python Dance made landmark achievement in the area of ensuring non-congestion roads for easy phase (Python Dance 1) in the year 2016. Empirical assessment shows that the Niger Bridge head and other parts of Anambra State that usually experienced heavy traffic congestion during the yuletide were free for travellers during the Christmas celebration in 2016, unlike the ugly experience had between October and December, 2017.

ii. Reduction in Violent Crimes: Some of the security challenges that were posing so much threat to the people of the South-East such as armed robbery, kidnapping, hostage taking, abduction, communal clashes, herdsmen/farmers clashes, secessionist attacks etc, were reduced to the barest minimum. For instance, residents of Umuahia, the capital of Abia State and Aba, the commercial hubs of the state despite have mixed feelings over the presence of the soldiers in the state believed that the presence of the soldiers is worthwhile because the state has witnessed relative peace since they were deployed in the state for an operation code names 'Python Dance'. More so, Mr. Franklin Chukwunazaekpere, who lives along Uratta by Aba-portharcourt expresses way told news men that the residents of the area now sleep with their two eyes closed in the last two weeks to the presence of the soldiers, (The Nation, 2017).

iii. Free Medical Out-reach: The military during Operation Python Dance, offered free medical out-reach to over 800 Indigene and non-indigenes of Azia community in Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra State. According to Regional Medical Officer in-charge of the Medical outreach, Captain Casmir Okpe, said the common ailments of the people are hypertension and arthritis among the elderly, while malaria and upper respiratory tract infection (cough) were predominant among the children, (Vanguard, 2016).

However, the function between the military authorities and innocent civilians provided the need for safety measures apart from the three (3) days curfew declared in Abia

State by the state government were as follows:

- a. Always carry your identity card with you so that you can always identify yourself whenever called upon to do so.
- b. Never, stay out late for whatever reason.
- c. If you must drive, ensure your driver license and all car particulars are complete and valid.
- d. If possible, do not drive a car with tinted glass even if you have a police permit.
- e. If you are stopped at the check point, answer only the question that you are asked. Do not volunteer any information nor ask questions.
- f. Do not for any reason argue with any military personnel.
- g. Stay indoors as much as possible, go out only when it is absolutely necessary.
- h. Do not play football on the street or road side.
- i. Do not jog on the street or road side.
- j. Do not for any reason carry any Biafra souvenirs with you.
- k. Do not play loud music in your car while driving.
- l. Avoid fixing weddings, burials or any form of function that will require the gathering of many people.
- m. Wear clothings that can cover up your tattoos if possible.

n. Females should as much as possible move around in pairs among other precautionary measures.

4.3 Political Impacts of Operation Python Dance in the South-East

The following are some of the crucial political related impacts of the military's exercise (Egwu-Eke) in the Southeastern part of Nigeria.

i. Political Stability: It is germane to state that the military drill by the Nigeria Army was efficient in ensuring political stability in the Southeast. Some political experiences prior to the first episode of the military exercise in 2016 such as violent agitations by separatist group, shooting amongst cult groups, abduction of political opponents, police and IPOB clashes , deliberate vandalism of security personnel vehicles etc, were drastically reduced to the barest minimum following the wake of Operation Python Dance in the zone.

Today, people can now freely walk through the roads and streets without fear of molestation and also go about their lawful business without threat or harassment by miscreants which was never a guarantee in the past.

ii. Promotes Political Education: Both episodes of the military exercise (Operation Python Dance I & II) improves the body of political knowledge at the individual level. Collectively, the mass public become more politically aware and enlightened on the

inalienable military-civilian relationship in a given society. By virtue of the military exercise, inhabitants of the Southeast zone become more aware of their fundamental human rights and more exposed on how to tackle issues of human right violation.

Basically, the Operation Python Dance was with laudable remarks. Meanwhile, it defies logic to state that the exercise carried out by the Nigeria Army did not paint an ugly picture especially, on the fundamental human rights of the citizens; their Rules of Engagement (ROE) was condemned outright, because it was an advertisement of excessive show of force.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

To sum it up, it becomes pertinent to reiterate that the military institution is one of the principle institution in a sovereign-state. It aims at promoting and maintaining peace and stability in the state.

Therefore, the military's Operation Python Dance exercise was efficient in combating violent crimes and agitations in the South-East, Nigeria. Hitherto, which have distorted peace and order in the zone.

However, in the light of the foregoing together with the appreciation of structural-functional theory as the researcher's theoretical framework of analysis, the following are the findings:

- i. Operation Python Dance exercise embarked upon by the Nigeria Army in the Southeast was legal and constitutional.
- ii. Operation Python Dance exercise was efficient in the maintenance of peace and stability to a reasonable extent with sheer brute Force within the intervals of the exercise in the Southeast.
- iii. The character of the men of the military during the Operation Python Dance II does not in any way confirm with the rules of engagement (ROE) of the Nigeria Armed Forces in civil-related matters as stipulated in Section 8(1) and (3) of the Armed Forces Act, 2014 laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN).
- iv. More so, Operation Python Dance 2 unlike the first episode (Python Dance 1) held in 2016, over looked the primary and place of the civilians such as traditional rulers, chieftains, ethnic groups and religious bodies whose intelligence report would have helped to eliminate violent crimes and bringing a lasting peace in the region.
- v Finally, the Operation Python Dance significantly impacted on the economic, social and political networks in the region by providing strong and adequate security system in the face of criminality, violent crimes and agitations. Nevertheless, some of these crimes such as cultism, arm banditry, proliferation of light and small arms, communal clashes, herdsman-farmers clashes are still common within the zone.

5.3 Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were made;

- i. The military should be made to undergo serious training geared towards internal security operations before engaging them into similar task. More so, re-training is also important to meet with the recent challenges of sophisticated global threat,
- ii. There is urgent need for adequate security especially, in the rural areas. Meanwhile, the military should collaborate with civilians and civil authorities such as civil society organizations, religious bodies, ethnic/traditional groups etc. Intelligence gathering is a veritable force for crime prevention and control,
- iii. There should be re-orientation campaign of soldiers involved in internal peace operation and the entire populace as well. The military has been tagged with a label of terror and an average Nigerian encountering soldiers on the road is likely to be subjected to unnecessary and unwarranted fear.
- iv. Instead of embarking on a show of force, the military in collaboration with civil authorities should carry out programmes aimed at exposing and acquainting the public especially, the youths on creativity and vocational skills. By so doing, there will be job providers other than job seekers. Vocational and technical education should be vigorously pursued. This will go a long way to reduce youth restiveness. This is because crime is a challenge that all and sundry must confront head on for a stable and peace society and,

v. Finally, for effective and efficient performance and success of the above mentioned, the Federal need to increase it's funding especially, the police and other civil security agencies so to procure modern and adequate equipment to combat violent crimes in the region. More so, such funds are to be properly monitored to avoid diversion into private pockets and also, rid the Nigeria military and police of it's corrupt elements.

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APPENDIX

Since President Muhammadu Buhari assumed the reins of leadership in May, 2015, the army has dug up quite some queer code names as it continues to protect the nation's territorial integrity.

The Nigeria Army embarked on the following exercises:

1. Operation Lafia Dole:

This code name literally translates to "Peace by all means" in Hausa language.

Operation Lafia Dole is the Army's code name for the war on terror in Nigeria's Northeast.

It was launched by Chief of Army Staff, Major Gen. Tukur Buratai in July 2015 as a replacement of "Operation Zaman Lafiya" (Let's live in peace).

2. Operation Sharan Daji:

This operation was launched in July 2015 to tackle recurring incidents of livestock rustling and armed banditry in the Northwest region of Nigeria.

3. Operation Awatse:

Launched in the Southwest to tackle militants and oil installations vandals around Arepo, Ishawo and Elepete creeks in Lagos and Ogun states.

Awatse translates to "Scatter" in Hausa language.

Operation Awatse was implemented by a combined team from the Airforce and Navy with plenty of support from Army boots on the ground.

4. Operation Shirin Harbi:

Launched in 2015 to combat restiveness in Bauchi and Gombe states.

Shirin Harbi was also useful as the military sought to rein in the killers in Southern Kaduna.

5. Harbin Kunama I:

This was the military's answer to cattle rustling and armed banditry in the Dansadau Forest of Zamfara state and environs.

Harbin Kunama translate to "sting of a scorpion" in Hausa language.

It was a Northwest operation launched in 2015.

6. Crocodile Smile I:

This was a South-south operation flagged off in August, 2015.

It aim is to improve operational effectiveness in the creeks and halt the destructive activities of oil thieves and militants.

This operation sought to rein Niger Delta militants crippling Nigeria's oil installations.

7. Operation Python Dance I:

A Southeast operation with Anambra state as it base.

Operation Python Dance translates Egwu-Eke in Igbo language.

It lasted over a month and its objective was to check the spread of robbery, kidnapping and cultism in and around Anambra state.

8. Harbin Kunama II:

Northwest and North-central operation launched in July, 2017.

Its brief was similar to Harbin Kunama I- dealt with cattle rustlers, armed bandits and limited herders/farmers clashes.

9. Operation Dokaji:

Another Northwest and North-central drill with similar objectives to Harbin Kunama. Launched in July, 2017.

10. Operation Python Dance II:

Egwu-Eke II as it was called in the Southeast, was with the mandate to check issues of kidnapping, robbery, cultism and of course secessionist agitations in the zone. Abia state is its operational base.

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